

IMPROVING ENGLISH VOCABULARY FOR STUDENTS THROUGH LISTENING TO ENGLISH NEWS

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ABSTRACT

The major aim of the present research is to investigate the effects of listening To English News on improving the vocabulary of English majors at a Universities Worldwide. The researcher called for 60 students to volunteer to Take part in the study, 30 of whom were assigned to the experimental group And the other half assigned to the control group. The two groups had to Respond to the pre-questionnaire and take the pre-test on vocabulary. The Experimental group then entered the experimental process and was asked to Listen to English News every day to learn vocabulary. Besides, they did some Exercises designed by the researcher related to the English News they heard.

Data were collected within ten weeks via the pre-questionnaire, the pre-test, The post-test and the post-questionnaire. The results of the study indicated that The experimental group advanced remarkably in terms of vocabulary Compared to the control group. This demonstrated that listening to English News has a positive effect on English majors' vocabulary. The results of the Post-questionnaire also reveal that the students' feedback on the practice Listening to English News is generally positive.

Keywords: English vocabulary, English major, English news, Listening skill, New words, post-test, Post-questionnaire, pre-question, Vocabulary, Glossary, Wilkin, Verbal, No-verbal, Gestures.

1.INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary learning is a significant part of second or foreign language learning Because without adequate vocabulary learners cannot understand others or express their own Ideas. Vocabulary is also important for learning to read, write, listen and speak. Wilkins (1972) claimed that while without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary Nothing can be aconveyed. Nation (2001) added that if students lack vocabulary, their ability To comprehend or express themselves clearly is limited. Therefore, "vocabulary acquisition is Central to language acquisition, whether the language is first, second, or foreign." (Decarrico, 2001) Being aware of the importance of vocabulary in learning languages, especially English, most of the students spend a lot of time learning it.However, a common problem in learning vocabulary is that students have limited access to authentic materials. There are several slightly different definitions for the term "authentic materials" in the Literature. For example, Krashen (1982) defined authentic materials as "the natural Communication task". Rogers (1988) described authentic materials as "appropriate and Quality" in terms of goals,

objectives, learners' needs and interests and "natural" in terms of Real life and meaningful communication. Jordon (1997) refers to authentic materials as "texts That are not written for language teaching purposes." Kilikaya (2004) defined authentic Materials as "exposure to real language and use in its community." Researchers have also Realized some of the advantages of using authentic materials in EFL classrooms and English News are among those materials. Authentic materials can provide learners with intensive Exposure to real language, and they are related more closely to students' needs and interests; As a result, students can be exposed to real-world intercultural discourse (Kilickaya, 2004; Martinez, 2002; Peacock, 1997)

The research aims to help English majors at a university in Vietnam widen their Vocabulary in various topics in an authentic manner through listening to English News. The Aim of this study was investigated through the following research questions: (1). What is the Current situation of learning vocabulary among English majors? And (2). To what extent has English majors' vocabulary improved through listening to English News?

2.RATIONALE FOR USING ENGLISH NEWS IN IMPROVING ENGLISH VOCABULARY

This section details the rationale for using English news to improve students' Vocabulary

2.1. English News Provides the Authentic Context for Learning New Words

Wallace (1992) defines authentic materials as real-life materials, which are originally Not designed for academic purposes. Apart from official teaching materials, teachers can Make good use of these authentic resources and gain huge benefits for teaching English. Bloom(2000) stated that human beings can learn new words in the context they hear The words and based on that linguistic context they can work out what these new words mean. As a result, English news can be a good way for students to learn new vocabulary. Pieces of English news are basically concerned about normal issues in our everyday Life and students can easily access them via social media such as is, radio, youtube, Facebook and other websites. These pieces of news might have come from a local Vietnamese Newspaper or an English-language television show. Therefore, when listening to English News, students are able to guess the meanings of the new English words from context and Predict the main contents with this background knowledge.

2.2. English News Can Provide Not Only Audio But Also Visual Elements

Several researchers have claimed that extra-linguistic information may significantly Impact comprehension. Oxford us (1990) declared that almost all language learners can Associate new pieces of information with the previouslyknown concepts in their memory With the aid of meaningful visual images, which helps improve their learning efficiency. It Has been demonstrated that students learn more quickly with visual clues q they would With words alone. Additionally, more brain regions are engaged when visual and verbal Elements are combined, resulting in increased cognitive capacity.In 1988, Snyder and Colon conducted a research project to examine the effect of Audio-visual aids on enhancing language acquisition. For seven weeks, two groups of Participants were taught under two different conditions. The control group was taught with The standard curriculum in which limited amounts of audio-visual aids were employed. Meanwhile, the curriculum for the experimental group included audio tapes, PowerPoint Slides, bulletin boards, posters, pictures, and flash cards, among other audio-visual elements. Both groups were tested, and the group that received more audio-visual aids performed Significantly better in terms of vocabulary retention.

According to Schmitt (2008) children need motivation to become active learners as Without motivation, they cannot learn effectively. Zhang (2009) investigated the situation of Learning foreign language vocabulary among 481 university students regarding their beliefs, Strategies and size of the vocabulary. The findings indicate that students preferred to learn Vocabulary in real-world situations. He also said that teachers should help students choose And use learning strategies that work best for their learning styles and preferences.

2.4. English News Can Provide Learners with a Rich Source of Comprehensible Input

The researcher would like to demonstrate that English news can satisfy the abovementioned requirements. By watching or listening to English news, learners can use their Background knowledge, the images and the sounds to understand the messages and learn the Target language's vocabulary. The researchers believe that speaking is a process of Expressing ideas in the spoken language, and it is one of the most challenging aspects of Language because it requires basic skills such as pronunciation, fluency, grammar, and Vocabulary. Widdowson (1985) also said that vocabulary, frequency of practice, functional Grammar, relevant subjects, motivation, self-confidence, and situation are all factors that Influence students' speaking ability.

Students' Feedback on Using English News to Improve Vocabulary

A post-experiment questionnaire was given to only the experimental group at the end Of the experimental time. The aim of the post-questionnaire was to investigate students' Opinions and attitudes about learning vocabulary through listening to English News and their Suggestions to enhance the effectiveness of using English News to improve vocabulary. In the Design of the questions, the researcher combined two types of items: open-ended questions. And closeended questions. The researcher applied open-ended questions to exploit more Information from the respondents. Regarding interest in listening to English News to enhance their vocabulary, most of The students (87%) indicated that they found English News an interesting source for them to Improve their vocabulary. Regarding the benefits of English News, most of the students (77%) stated that Listening to English News brings them many benefits in the process of learning vocabulary. Half of the students stated that they could learn almost all aspects of vocabulary and have More chances to learn vocabulary through many topics. Therefore, their vocabulary was Improved significantly. Students also know how to use some words in certain situations; Furthermore, they feel comfortable when listening to English News to learn vocabulary. In addition, more than half of the students agreed that they will always or usually Continue listening to English News to improve their vocabulary; 43% of the students Indicated that sometimes they use listening to English News to improve their vocabulary. In Particular, no students chose the category of "Never".

Techniques of Teaching Vocabulary: The first step in teaching vocabulary is to determine the nature and relative difficulty of the Word. There are many English words, e.g. pen, ball, bag, table etc. Which have already Entered pupils" mother tongue. There are other words e.g. father, mother, sun, moon, cat, Dog, eat, and drink which have at least in their meanings, exact equivalentents in their mother Tongue. When we teach the vocabulary to SL learners we try to give the meaning in their Mother tongue, teach the spelling, meaning in mother tongue, and teach the spelling the Forms(singular/plural, past/present etc.in the case of irregular nouns and verbs) and the Pronunciation. Figurative and transferred meaning of the words will require special treatment. But there are many other words in English which have they exact

translation equivalents. Therefore these kinds of words would be difficult for the pupils. Most of the structural words And other high frequency words come under this category. There are some techniques of

Teaching vocabulary are as follows:

✓ Actual objects or models: At classroom teacher can be taught names of many Things by showing actual objects or models.

✓ Actions: The meaning of many words can be made clear by performing simple Actions in the classroom e.g. walk, using body gestures.

Pictures: The use of pictures for teaching vocabulary is quite obvious; every good Dictionary makes use of them. Learner"s can learn any word with the help of Suitable picture, e.g. big, eyes, hand, man, woman etc.

✓ Blackboard sketches: Quick blackboard sketches may work in teaching Vocabulary. Learner"s can easily understand the meaning of the word, it will Helpful to develop the vocabulary.

✓ Verbal Context: There are many abstract words and the meaning of which cannot Presented by visual means. Such a technique is creating verbal context with known Words, e.g. (a) I like tea more than coffee. I prefer tea to coffee.

✓ Illustrative Sentence: An illustrative sentence is very helpful for showing the Usage of word, and every good dictionary makes the use of such kind of sentence And use them after the pupils have grasped the general meaning of the word, e.g. Accept. (a)The captain of the team acceptedrefers judgment without protest.

✓ Synonyms: If the learner"s can be already known the acceptable synonym, it can Be used in a sentence to teach the meaning of the new word, e.g. pretty (a) the girl Is a pretty.

✓ Antonyms: Antonyms like the synonyms, an antonym can also be used in a Sentence by pupil, if it is already known them.

✓ Translation and Explanation: These two seem to be the top favorites with teachers. But it will have been clear that they are at least satisfactory means of teaching Vocabulary. Translation and explanation in pupil"s mother tongue should be Attempted only when the other means discussed above have been found Inadequate or unnecessarily time consuming.

3.CONCLUSION:

The acquisition of vocabulary is arguably the most critical component of successful language Learning. Until recently, however, it has been difficult to determine the most important Phrases and words needed to establish a suitable vocabulary for conducting conversationmost effectively. The task at hand, therefore, is to talk this new information and apply it in The classroom.

Since there are so many things to learn about to teach piece of Vocabulary(meaning, spoken/written forms, collocations, connotations, grammar etc.) it is Important that we as teachers only introduce a little at a time, starting with the most frequent, Useful, and less frequent uses of o'previously learned items. This paper tries to give them some Techniques and methods to build ESL learner"s knowledge of vocabulary.Based on the results of the pre-questionnaire and the vocabulary pre-test it can be seen That students encounter many difficulties in learning vocabulary. Besides, although English News is available on a lot of social media, many students rarely listen to English News to learn vocabulary. In addition, the

results of the vocabulary pretest and post-test show that There is a significant difference in the pre and post-test scores of the experimental group. Meanwhile, for the control group, the difference between the mean pre-test score and the Mean post-test score was much smaller (11,2 as compared to 4,9). This demonstrates that Although the experiment was implemented in a short time of ten weeks, the vocabulary of the Students in the experimental group improved much more considerably than that of the control Group. Finally, by analyzing students' postquestionnaire responses, the researcher found out. That listening to English News could raise students' interest and impulse to learn vocabulary.

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